

Bṛhatkālottara, vāstuyāgapāṭala (BK vy), edition.

J DSCN JPG1222 lower line 6 (the foliation is patchy, and often missing at this point in the text. I will, therefore, refer to the digital image numbers); K f226v, line 2; A f259v, line 2; H f245r, line 5.

- 1 kṣetramānaṃ bhūparīkṣā vāstuyāgo nirucyate
ekadvitriśataṃ kṣetraṃ hīnaṃ madhyama cottamam J1223upper; Hf245v
- 2 kodaṇḍānāṃ pramāṇena śodhanīyaṃ śikhidhvaja
sitā raktā tathā pītā kṛṣṇā viprādiṣu sthitā
- 3 pradakṣiṇodakā śastā supuṣpadrumabhūṣitā
ramyā sugandhā madhurā hīnasattvavivarjitā
- 4 antyajuṣṭā parityājyā ūṣarāśikatākulā
duṣṭapraṇivṛtā tyājyā tathā sudūrodakānvitā
- 5 ā vāridarśanāt śodhyā śalyahīnāthavā yathā
urvī tathā vidhātavyā kuṭṭayed dhastipādakaiḥ

$\Omega = AHKJ(\rightarrow D)$, $\alpha = KJ(\rightarrow D)$, $\beta = AH$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

- 1a mānaṃ] AH; pālaṃ JK • parīkṣā] AHK; carīkṣā J
1b yāgo] JK; yāgaṃ AH 1c tri] HJK; ṭṛ A
1d hīnaṃ] H; hīna AJK • madhyama] AJK; madhyamaṃ H
2a kodaṇḍānāṃ] JKH; kādaṇḍānāṃ A
2b śodhanīyaṃ] AJK; śocanīyaṃ H • dhvaja] AHK; dvaja J
2c raktā] AHK; rakta J 2d sthitā] AJ; sthitāḥ HK
3c madhurā] AJK; [-]dhurā H
4a antya] AJK; a[-] H
• juṣṭā] conj. Sanderson; jyaṣṭā JK; [[jā]]{ja}ṣṭhā A; jāṣṭau H
4b ūṣarā] em.; ū[[pa]]{ṣa}rā A; [-]ṣarā J; [-]ṣarādha K; jaṣarā H
• śikatākulā] JKH; śikatālukā A
5a ā vāri] JK; avāri A; ācāri H
5c vidhātavyā] AH; vidhākāryā K; vidhāvāryā J
5d dhasti] AJK; dhasi H • pādakaiḥ] HJK; vādakaiḥ A

- 6 udakpūrvaplavā śastā tathā puṣpodakānvitā
darpaṇodarasaṃkāśā kartavyā śilpipuṃgavaiḥ
- 7 tatrādau gaṇayāgaṃ kāryaṃ kṣetraparigrahe Kf227r
digīśebhyo baliṃ dattvā tato homaṃ samācaret Af260r
- 8 homāvasāne cihnāni jñātvā śalyaṃ samuddharet
divyāntarikṣacihnāni jñātvā samyag vidhānataḥ
- 9 duṣṭaśalyaṃ vijānīyāt pāpe horāgate sati Hf246r
dhvajo raviḥ samādiṣṭo dehināṃ mūrdhni saṃsthitaḥ J1223lower
- 10 saṃsparśāc chubhaśalyaṃ tu sthapatyācāryakartṛṣu
mukho dhūmo mato bhaumaḥ śalyaṃ asthimayaṃ vadet

$\Omega = \text{AHKJ}(\rightarrow\text{D})$, $\alpha = \text{KJ}(\rightarrow\text{D})$, $\beta = \text{AH}$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

6a udak] A; udaka HJK

7a tatrādau] AHJ; tatrādaur K 7b kṣetraparigrahe] AK; kṣetraṃparigra[-] J;

between kṣetra and parigrahe H enters and then strikes out the following portion from verses 4 and 5: [[tyājyājaṣarāsikatākulā | duṣṭaprāṇīvr̥tātyājyātathāsudūrodakānvitā | ācāridarśanā]]

7c baliṃ] AHK; bali J 8a cihnāni] AJK; cihāni H

8b śalyaṃ] AJK; [-]lyam H

8c divyāntarikṣa] JK; divyaṃtarikṣa A; divyāntariṣa H • cihnāni] AJK; vihāni H

8d samyag] A; samyak JK; samyaka H 9a duṣṭa] AHJ; duṣṭam K

9c samādiṣṭo] A; samāviṣṭo HJK

10a saṃsparśāc chubha] JK; saṃsparśā[[ḍu]]{cchu}ba A; saṃsparśāsubha H

10b after sthapa J repeats the previous passage from 8d on. The passage repeated is exactly the portion covered by the second line of manuscript K's f227r.

10c mukho] AJ; mukhau K; ṣukho H • dhūmo] HJK; [[sū]]{dhū}mo A

• mato] AJ; matau HK 10d mayam] AH; tāyam JK

- 11 siṃhas tu bhārgavo jñeyo bhujābhyāṃ vakṣasi sthitaḥ
śvā budhaḥ kroḍagaḥ puṇyaṃ liṅgaṃ jīvo vṛṣātmakaḥ
- 12 kharāḥ śanis tu vijñeyo kaṭyurubhyāṃ vyavasthitaḥ
gajaṃ candrādhidaivatyaṃ jaṅghābhyāṃ ca vyavasthitam
- 13 dhvāṅkṣe rāhuḥ samādiṣṭaḥ pādābhyāṃ tu susaṃsthitaḥ
yad aṅgaṃ sprṣate tatra tadaṅge śalyam ādiṣet
- 14 dhvāṅkṣagardabhadhūmeṣu asthiśalyaṃ samādiṣet
dhvaje gaje śubhaṃ śalyaṃ siṃhe madhyaṃ vṛṣe śubham
- 15 adhamaṃ budhahorāyāṃ tatra tatra tathā labhet Kf227v
tasmin deśe tatpramāṇaṃ śalyam āhur manīṣiṇaḥ

$\Omega = \text{AHKJ}(\rightarrow\text{D}), \alpha = \text{KJ}(\rightarrow\text{D}), \beta = \text{AH}$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

J has a lacuna from 11c after śvā to 13a before kharāhu

Folio 227v of K is very hard to read in the copy I have. I will work mainly from A and J between 15c and 22c.

11a bhārgavo] AJK; bhārpavo H

11b vakṣasi sthitaḥ] HK; vakṣasisthitaṃ J; vakṣursisthiteḥ A

11c budhaḥ] K; budho AH • kroḍagaḥ] HK; kroḍagaṃ A

11d vṛṣātmakaḥ] HK; [[mṛtā]]{vṛṣā}tmakaḥ A

12b kaṭyurubhyāṃ] em.; ka[-]rubhyāṃ K; kaṭyūrūbhyā H; kaṭyūruṃvyā A

12c candrādhidaivatyaṃ] A; candrādhidevatyaṃ K; caṃdrāvidevatyaṃ H

13a dhvāṅkṣe rāhuḥ] AHK; [-]kharāhu J

• samādiṣṭaḥ] HK; samāddiṣṭaḥ A; samādiṣṭa J

13b pādābhyāṃ] A; padābhyāṃ HJK

• tu su] conj. Sanderson; tṛṣu JK; triṣu H; [[viṃ]]{tri}ṣu A

13c aṅgaṃ] JK; aṅga H; agaṃ A 13d tad] AJK; [-]d H • aṅge] HJK; agaṃ A

14c dhvaje] HK; dhva[[sta]]{je} A; dhvaja J • gaje] JK; ga[[jo]]{je} A; gajo H

• śubhaṃ] JKH; stubhaṃ A

14d siṃhe madhyaṃ vṛṣe] AK; siṃhemadhyevṛṣe H; siṃhamadhyavṛṣa J

15a adhamaṃ] AJK; avamaṃ H • budha] AJK; budhe H

15c tasmin] HA; tasmina J • pramāṇaṃ] J; pramāṇam AH

- 16 pratipattithiṣv apy eva sūryādyāḥ samparibhramāt
rātrau pañcavidhaṃ tena digīśaṃ syāt tadardhataḥ
- 17 ardhapraharikā jñeyā tadā śalyaṃ samuddharet
āvāridarśanaṃ pūjyaṃ vāstudehaṃ prayatnataḥ
- 18 mahāratnair vidhānaṃ tu sthāpayitvā prapūrayet
pūrayitvā ca saṃkuṭṭya kṛtvā darpaṇasaṃnibham
- 19 samapṛṣṭhe punar vāstuṃ samāṃśenaiva vartayet
catuḥṣaṣṭipadaṃ punar vāstuṃ nāparaṃ hitam
- 20 koṇe 'rdhapadikān aṣṭau śeṣāṃs tu padikān viduḥ
nyāsaṃ ca madhyataḥ kāryaṃ pūjādhyānādikaṃ sadā

Af260v

J1224upper

Hf246v

$\Omega = \text{AHKJ}(\rightarrow D)$, $\alpha = \text{KJ}(\rightarrow D)$, $\beta = \text{AH}$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

16a pratipattithiṣv] H; pratipattithiṣv A; pratipattitheṣv J

• apy eva] A; apyevaṃ HJ 16b sūryādyāḥ] HJ; sūryā[[yā]]{dyāḥ} A

16c vidhaṃ tena] HJ; vidhaṃte{na} A

16d digīśaṃ] HJ; di[[mī]]{gī}śaṃ A • syāt] HJ; syā[[cca]] A

• ardhatāḥ J; a[[ṃta]]{rddha}taḥ A; aṃtataḥ H

17a jñeyā] A; jñeyāḥ HJ 17c vāri] J; cāri AH • darśanaṃ] em. Sanderson;

darśane AHJK • pūjyaṃ] AJ; pūjya H

17d vāstudehaṃ] H; vā{stu}deheca A; vāstuṃ caiva J

18a ratnair] H; ratnai A; ratne J 18b prapūrayet] tentative conj. Sanderson;

prapūjayet AH; tupūjayet JK

18c pūrayitvā] AH; pūjayitvā J • ca] A; tu HJ

• saṃkuṭṭya] AH; saṃkuḍya J

18d darpaṇasaṃnibham] A; darpaṇasaṃnibhāṃ H; darppanasannibhāṃ J

19a vāstuṃ] AH; vāstu J

19b samāṃśenaiva] A; samānenaiva J; samāśenaiva H

19c catuḥ] AHK; catu J

19d nāparaṃ] JK; nāpare AH

At 20ab H reads: koṇerddhapadikā[- - - - -]ciduḥ

20a koṇe 'rdhapadikān aṣṭau] em.; koṇārdhapadikānaṣṭau A;

koṇearddhapatikāṣṭausyāc] J 20b śeṣāṃs] em.; cheṣās AJ • padikān] A; padikā J

20c ca madhyataḥ kāryaṃ] A; tumadhyatakāryaṃ H; tumadhyatakārya J

- 21 madhye catuṣpade brahmā caturvaktraś caturbhujah
kamaṇḍalvakṣasūtrī ca daṇḍī viṣṭaramaṇḍitaḥ
- 22 haṃsārūḍho bṛhatkuṣiḥ kamalopariṣaṃsthiḥ
praṇavena namo'ntena sampūjyas tu svasaṃjñāyā
- 23 ṣaṭpadaḥ pūrvadigbhāge sa marīcir vyavasthiḥ Kf228r
vajraprāsadharah śrīmān carmapāśadharas tathā
- 24 dvinetraś caikavaktraś ca taptacāmīkaraprabhaḥ
pratyālīḍhasamāviṣṭo nānābhūṣaṇabhūṣitaḥ

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21a catuṣpade] HJ; catuḥpado A

21b caturvaktraś] AH; catuvaktraś J

• caturbhujah] AH; catubhujah J

21d viṣṭara] A; viṣṭura J; viṣṭra H • maṇḍitaḥ] JH; maṇḍitā A

22a haṃsārūḍho] H; haṃsāmrūḍha J; haṃsārū[-] A

22c namo'ntena] HJ; [[tatovedā]]{namontena} A

22d sampūjyastu] JHK; sampūjyaṃca A

23b marīcir] em.; marīci A; marīco JK; marīṣo H

23c vajra] AJK; va[-] H • prāsa] HK; p[[r]]āsaṃ A; pāśa J

• śrīmān] AJ; śrīmāna HK

24c pratyālīḍhasamāviṣṭo] em.; pratyālīḍhasamāviṣṭā JK; [[kapālāḍhasamāviṣṭo]]
{pratyālīḍhasamāviṣṭā} A; pratyālīḍḍasamāviṣṭo H

25	vivasvān dakṣiṇe bhāge ṣaṭpado vāstudehagaḥ ekavaktras trinetrāś ca bhinnāñjanasamadyutiḥ	J1224lower Af261r
26	dvibhujo mahiṣārūḍho daṇḍapāśakarārpitaḥ paścime vāstudehasya ṣaṭpade mitranāyakaḥ	Hf247r
27	himakundendusamkāśas trinetrāś ca caturbhujāḥ pāśāṅkuśadharo raudraḥ kuntahasto mahābalaḥ	
28	ālīḍhasthānasamsthāno bhrtyakoṭisamanvitaḥ pṛthivīdharasamjñas tu vāstor uttaradiggataḥ	
29	caturbhujai kavaktrāś ca trinetro mukuṭānvitaḥ candragauro mahāprāṇo vaiṣṇavāsanapadmadr̥k	
30	śaraśāraṅgahastaś ca tathā musalabhūṣitaḥ nānābharaṇasampannaḥ sadā bhīmasasainyakaḥ	

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In the margin, A corrects from trinetrāś at 27c to samanvitaḥ at 28b, as follows:

[[trinetrāścaturbhujāḥ | pāśāṅkuśadharoraudraḥkuṃtahastimahīrataḥ |
ālīḍhayānasacatobhrtyakoṭisamanvitaḥ]] {trinetrāścaturbhujāḥ |
pāśāṅkuśadharoraudraḥkuntahastomahābalaḥ | ālīḍhasthānasamcchannobhrtyakoṭisamanvitaḥ}

- 25b ṣaṭpado] A; padetu HJK 25c vaktras] AHK; vaktra J
 26a bhujō] HJK; bhajo A • ārūḍho] HJK; ārū{ḍho} A
 26b pāśa] AH; vyāśa KJ
 26c paścime] HJK; paścimā A • dehasya] A; dehetu H; dehastu JK
 27a samkāśas] AH; samkāśa JK 27b catur] AHK; catu J
 27d hasto] HJK; [[hasti]]{hasto} A
 • mahābalaḥ] HJK; [[mahīrataḥ]]{mahābalaḥ} A
 28a sthāna] HJK; [[yāna]]{sthāna} A
 • samsthāno] conj.; samcchanno HJK; [[sacato]]{samcchanno} A
 28c samjñas] AJK; samjas H
 28d vāstor uttara] A; vāsturuttara HJ; vāsturudrattara K
 29a catur] AHK; catu J • vaktrāś] AHK; vaktrāś J
 29b netro] AHK; netrā J • mukuṭānvitaḥ] HK; makuṭānvitaḥ J; takaṭānvitaḥ A
 29c gauro] HK; [[syaiva]]{gauro} A; gauno J
 30a śāraṅga] JKA; sāragam H
 30b musala] AKH; mukhala J • bhūṣitaḥ] AH; bhūṣitaḥ JK
 30d sasainyakaḥ] AH; sasainyaka K; sasyanyaka J

- 31 īśadikpadiko hy āpas trivakraḥ ṣaḍbhujas tathā
randhralocanapadmābhaś cakrakuntagadādharah Kf228v
- 32 śaraśāraṅgasamṇaddhaḥ koṭipramathasamṇyutaḥ
āpavatsas tathā jñeyaḥ taddikpadikasamsthitaḥ
- 33 candragauravibhaḥ kiṃ tu maṇḍalasthānakasthitaḥ
tathā dr̥ṣṭānusāreṇa rasabhāvakarānvitaḥ J1225upper
- 34 āpavad āpavatsaś ca vaktrāyudhavikalpanam Af261v
savitā padiko jñeyaḥ sāvitṛī padikas tathā
- 35 indraīndrajayau tadvad rākṣasyāṃ diśi samsthitau
vāyavye rudradāsaś ca rudraś ca padikas tathā

$\Omega = AHKJ(\rightarrow D)$, $\alpha = KJ(\rightarrow D)$, $\beta = AH$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

H lacks 33ab

- 31a īśa] AHJ; iṣa K • padiko hy āpas] HJK; padakāṣṭhāpas A
31c randhra] A; randra JK; J; raṃpra H
• locana] JK; locanaṃ H; lo[[bha]]{ca}na A
• padmābhaś] HK; padmābhaśś A; padmābha J
32b koṭi] AJK; kauṭi H • pramatha] HJK; prathamathama A
• samṇyutaḥ] AJK; samṇvrataḥ H
32c āpavatsas] AJK; apavatsas H • jñeyaḥ] HJK; jñeyā A
32d taddikpadikasamsthitaḥ] conj.; svadikpadikasamsthitaḥ A;
tadigāntaspadikasthitaḥ JK; tadigāntaspādiksthitaḥ H
33a vibhaḥ] em.; vibha JK; nibhaḥ A
33b maṇḍala] KA; maṇḍalaṃ J • sthānaka] AK; sthāpaka J
33c dr̥ṣṭānusāreṇa] AH; dr̥ṣṭāntasāreṇa JK 33d rasa] AH; sarasa JK
• karānvitaḥ AHK; karānvitaṃḥ J
34c jñeyaḥ] HJK; jñeya A
34d sāvitṛī] JK; sāvitri AH
35a indraīndrajayau] JK; daṃḍaīndrajayau A; iṃdrajayautajjayo H
35c vāyavye] AJK; vāyavyo H

- 36 ditiśāv ardhapadikau khakṛśāv agnikoṣṭhakau mṛgaś ca pitā nairṛtyāṃ rogavāyū padārdhagau Hf247v
- 37 parjanyaadyāṃś ca padikān kathayāmi krameṇa tu parjanyaajayamahendrasūryasatyabhṛśās tathā
- 38 pūrvasyāṃ samsthitā hy ete dakṣiṇasyāṃ nigadyate pūṣā vitathasamjñāś ca tathā caiva gṛhakṣataḥ
- 39 yamo gandharvabhṛngaś ca dakṣiṇasyāṃ diśi sthitāḥ dauvārikaś ca sugrīvaḥ puṣpadantaḥ pracetasah
- 40 asuraḥ śoṣasamjñāś ca paścimasyāṃ diśi sthitāḥ nāgo mukhyo 'tha bhalvāṭaḥ somo ṛgyo 'ditiś tathā Kf229r
- 41 ete tu padikā jñeyā dhyānam āsāṃ nigadyate savitā raktavarṇābhāḥ khaḍgapāśakarārpitaḥ

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At A, 39cd and 40ab are inserted from the margin.

- 36a ditiśāv ardhā] A; digīśāuśarvva KJ; diśīśāusarvva H
 • padikau] JK; padagau AH
 36b khakṛśāv agni] conj.; khakṛśāñcagni HK; [[sva]]{kha}kṛśāṣvagni A; khakṛśāñcagnai J
 • koṣṭhakau] H; koṣṭhako K; koṣṭhagau A; koṣṭako J
 36c mṛgaś] JK; [[rom]]{mṛ}gaś A • pitā] em.; patī K; pat[[i]]{ī} A ; pati JH
 • nairṛtyāṃ] A; nairṛtyā JK; nnairṛtyāṃ H 36d vāyū] A; vāyu HJK
 37a parjanyaadyāṃś] K; parjjanyaadyāś J; paryanyaadyāś AH
 • padikān] em.; padikā AHJK
 37c parjanya] JK; paryanya AH
 • mahendra] em.; māhendra AHJK
 37d bhṛśās] HK; bhṛṃśās A; ruśān J
 38a pūrvasyāṃ] AHK; pūrvāsyāṃ J
 • samsthitā] AJK; [-]sthitā H • hy ete] AHK; hete J
 38b dakṣiṇasyāṃ] AHK; dakṣiṇāsyāṃ J
 38d gṛhakṣataḥ] JHK; gṛhakṣata A 39a bhṛngaś] AJK; bhīmaś H
 39b dakṣiṇasyāṃ] AHK; dakṣiṇāsyāṃ J 39b sthitāḥ] K; sthitā AHJ
 39c sugrīvaḥ] AJK; suyīve H 40b paścimasyāṃ] AHK; paścimā{syāṃ} J • sthitāḥ] AHK;

sthitā J

40c nāgo] A; nāga HJK • bhalvāṭaḥ] JK; bhallāṭaḥ A; bhalyāṭaḥ H

40d ṛgyo 'ditiś] em. Sanderson; ṛgāditiś JK; ṛgyaditiś AH

42	sāvitrisaṃjñakas tadvat kuśapīñjalakānvitaḥ indraḥ kāñcanavarṇābhāḥ trinetraḥ kuliśānvitaḥ	J1225lower
43	nīlendīvarahastaś ca yodhakoṭisamanvitaḥ tathaivendrajayaḥ kāryaḥ khaḍgapāśakarārpitaḥ	Af262r
44	rudraḥ kṛṣṇāñjanaprakhyāḥ śūlī khaḍgī trilocanaḥ tathā rudrajayaḥ kāryaḥ śaradaṇḍakaraḥ sadā	Hf248r
45	madhyāvaraṇasaṃsthāś ca kathitās te samāsataḥ bāhyāvaraṇasaṃsthāś ca kathayāmi śikhidhvaja	

$\Omega = \text{AHKJ}(\rightarrow\text{D})$, $\alpha = \text{KJ}(\rightarrow\text{D})$, $\beta = \text{AH}$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

At JK, 45cd is first inserted before verse 44, then repeated in its proper position.

42a sāvitrī] em. Sanderson; sāvitrīḥ BK vy 92a; sāvitrī AHJK

• tadvat] H; ta{dvat} A; tadvata JK

42b kuśa] AJK; kuśu H

43a nīlendī] AH; nīlenda JK

43b samanvitaḥ] AJK; samānvitaḥ H

43c jayaḥ] AHK; jaya J

44a rudraḥ] HJK; rudra A

• kṛṣṇāñjana] AJK; kṛṣṇāñjanaḥ H

44b trilocanaḥ] AHK; trilotrilocanaḥ J

43d karārpitaḥ] AJK; karārpitā H

45b samāsataḥ] AH; samā[-]taḥ K; samātataḥ J

45c bāhyāvaraṇa] HJK; bāhyāharaṇa A • saṃsthāś] AHK; saṃsthā J

45d dhvaja] AH; dhavaḥ JK

- 46 īsaṃ trinetaṃ śūlāsīcarmapañkajadhāriṇaṃ
ekavakraṃ trinayanaṃ kuntāsīsitavarṇakaṃ
- 47 nānācārī kṛtābhyāsaṃ parjanyaṃ meghavāhanaṃ
jayaś ca padmavarṇābho dhanurbāṇāsīcarmadhṛk Kf229v
- 48 indraḥ sahasranetraḥ tu kulīśāṅkuśabhūṣitaḥ
sūryaḥ sindūravārṇābho raśmīpadmakarārpitaḥ
- 49 satyaṃ padmadhvajākṛāntaṃ kuntaṃ ca vāmakare sthitaṃ J1226upper
satyaṃ caturmukhaṃ jñeyaṃ padmarāgasamaprabhaṃ
- 50 surūpaṃ yauvanopetaṃ vṛṣavakraṃ tu pañcamam
kamaṇḍaludharaṃ devaṃ daṇḍākṣāvalayānṛitaṃ
- 51ab rājīvāsanaṣṭhaṃ tu rājīvakarakalpitaṃ

$\Omega = \text{AHKJ}(\rightarrow D)$, $\alpha = \text{KJ}(\rightarrow D)$, $\beta = \text{AH}$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

- 46c trinayanaṃ] JK; sunayanaṃ AH
47b parjanyaṃ] AJK; paryanyaṃ H
47c varṇābho] AJK; parṇābho H
47d dhanurbāṇāsī] AH; dhanubāṇāsī JK
48a netras] AJK; netres H
48b kulīśāṅkuśa] AKH; kulīśāṃkuśa J
48c sūryaḥ] HJK; sūrya A
49a satyaṃ] H; satya JK; savye A
49b ca vāmakare] em.; [-]vāmakare A; c[-]āmakare H; [-]cāmgaṃkare K;
cepagakare J
49c catur] AHK; catu J • mukhaṃ] AJK; mukhā H
49d jñeyaṃ] AJK; jñeyā H 50a rūpaṃ] AHK; rūpa J
51b rājīvakara] AH; rājīvekara JK • kalpitaṃ] AJ; kalpitaḥ HK

- 51cd dāḍimīkusumaprahyaṃ bhṛṣam āścaryarūpiṇam
- 52 trisaptavadanaṃ devaṃ śatārdhakarakaḷpitam
diṇmukhaṃ tat prakartavyam uparyuparivaktrakam Af262v
- 53 uparyuparivaktrāṇāṃ kalayā hrāsam ādiśet
puruṣaṃ pūrvavaktraṃ tu bhairavaṃ dakṣiṇaṃ matam Hf248v
- 54 uttaraṃ vāmadevaṃ tu sadyojātaṃ tu paścimam
digrūpāṇi bhṛṣasyaiva vaktrāṇi kathitāni tu
- 55 atharvavedaṃ pūrvasyāṃ sāmavedaṃ tu dakṣiṇe
uttarasyāṃ yajurvedam ṛgvaktraṃ paścimaṃ matam

Ω = AHKJ(\rightarrow D), α = KJ(\rightarrow D), β = AH. (D not included in critical apparatus)

- 51c prakhyaṃ] AJK; prakṣyaṃ H
 51d rūpiṇam] AH; rūpiṇ[[ī]]am K; rūpiṇim J
 52a vadanam] AHJ; vadan[[ī]]am K
 52b śatārdha] AJK; śatārdhe H
 53c puruṣam] AH; puruṣa JK
 54b sadyojātaṃ] AKJ; sadyovātaṃ H
 • paścimam] paścimaṃ A; paścime HJK
 54c dig] AHK; rig J 55b dakṣiṇe] AHJ; dakṣiṇam K
 55c yajur] AHJ; yajar K 55d ṛg] AJK; ag H

- 56 prāguktavaktramānāni vikalāni mukhāni tu
vaikuṅṭhaṃ pūrvavadanaṃ narasiṃhaṃ tu dakṣiṇaṃ Kf230r
- 57 uttaraṃ caiva vārāhaṃ paścimaṃ kāpilaṃ sthitam
aṣṭāṅgulāni sarvāṇi yugmahānyā bhavanti hi J1226lower
- 58 indraṃ yamaṃ kuberaṃ ca varuṇaṃ paścimaṃ mukham
hānir atrāpi kartavyā kalayā kṛttikāsuta
- 59 ādityaṃ pūrvavadanaṃ āgneyaṃ dakṣiṇaṃ mukham
uttaraṃ candravadaṇaṃ pāṛthivaṃ paścimaṃ mukham
- 60 caturaṅgulamānāni kalāhānyā bhavanti hi
kalātmakaṃ vyomavakraṃ sarveṣāṃ uparisthitam

$\Omega = \text{AHKJ}(\rightarrow\text{D}), \alpha = \text{KJ}(\rightarrow\text{D}), \beta = \text{AH}$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

Between 57b and 57c, J and K insert 61a (which is later repeated in its proper position.)

- 56a mānāni] JK; mānā[[ntu]]ni A; mānānta H
56b vikalāni] AHK; [-]kalāni J
56d dakṣiṇaṃ] AJK; dākṣiṇaṃ H
57b kāpilaṃ] AH; kāpi[-] JK
58c hānir] HJK; hārir A
58d kalayā] AJK; kaṇayā H • suta] AH; sutaḥ JK
60a aṅgula] A; aṅgulaṃ JK; aṅguṇa H
60b kalā] AJK; ka[[lpa]]lā H • hānyā] H; hānyād HJK
60c kalātmakaṃ] A; kalāmekam HJK

61	ity evaṃ vaktrahrāsaṃ tu kāryam anyeṣu ṣaṇmukha khaḍgakuntaśarapāśadhanuścakrāsikheṭakam	Af263r
62	padmapattrākṣasūtram ca bijapūraṃ kamaṇḍalum halaṃ śaktigadāpāśaṃ daṇḍaṃ caiva paraśvadham	Hf249r
63	vīṇāṃ ca vallakīvaṃśavṛkṣacandrārkapatṭīśam pustakaṃ sruksruvau bhaṇḍīḍamaruṃ dhvajam eva ca	
64	kaṅkālāstraṃ mahāstraṃ ca brahmāstraṃ picchikaṃ tathā khādakāstram aghorāstraṃ śaṅkhabherīsamavitam	Kf230v
65	evamādyāni cānyāni bhṛśasya saṃprakalpayet nṛtyamānam atho vāpi kartavyaṃ parameśvaram	J1227upper

$\Omega = \text{AHKJ}(\rightarrow\text{D})$, $\alpha = \text{KJ}(\rightarrow\text{D})$, $\beta = \text{AH}$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

61b anyeṣu] AJK; anyaiṣu H

61c śara] HJK; śaraḥ A • pāśa] A; prāsa JK; prā[[pta]]sa H

61d dhanuś] AHK; dhanu J 62a pattrākṣa] AJK; pātrākṣa H

62b pūraṃ] AHK; pūra J

• kamaṇḍalum] AJ; kamaṇḍalum[[h]] K; kamaṇḍalaṃ H

62c halaṃ] JK; phalaṃ AH • śakti] HJK; śaktiṃ A • pāśa] HJK; pāśaṃ A

62d daṇḍaṃ] AH; daṇḍa JK

• paraśvadham] AJK; paraśvavaṃ H

63a vīṇāṃ] em.; vīṇā AHJK • vaṃśa] AJK; caṃsa H

63d patṭīśam] AJK; padisaṃ H

63c pustakaṃ] HJK; pustaka A

• sruksruvau] AJ; śrukaśruvau K; śrakaśruvau H

• bhaṇḍī] JK; bhaṅgī A; bhadri H

64b brahmāstraṃ] HJK; brahmāstraḥ A

• picchikaṃ JK piṃchakaṃ A; pisthikaṃ H

64c khādakāstram] JK; khātakāstram AH • aghorāstraṃ] AH; aghorā[-] JK

64d samanvitam] HJK; samanvitā A

65a ādyāni] JK; ādīni AH 65b bhṛśasya] JK; bhītāya A; bhīlpatraṃ H

• saṃprakalpayet] AJK; sāakalpayet H

- 66 nṛtyahastasamāyuktaṃ rasabhāvānvitaṃ haram
gatipracārasampannaṃ sthānakākṛāntamaṇḍalam
- 67 nānāṅghārasaṃyuktaṃ nānācārīvivartitam
lāsyatāṇḍavabhedena nānātodyasamanvitam
- 68 nānāsvarasamullāsais tumburādiṣu saṃsthitam
indrapadādisammiśraṃ ‡ jagatīyapadaīḥ ‡ punaḥ
- 69 ‡ ‡ nānāprastārabhedataḥ
śaḍjamadhyamagāndhāraṣabhaṃ caiva nāditam
- 70 svāṅgotthapṛavicārais tu layabhaṅgānusārataḥ
ity etad viśvarūpaṃ tu bhṛśākhyam te prakāśitam

Af263v

$\Omega = \text{AHKJ}(\rightarrow\text{D}), \alpha = \text{KJ}(\rightarrow\text{D}), \beta = \text{AH}$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

66a hasta] AJK; hantasta H

67a nānāṅga] AJK; nāmāga H • saṃyuktaṃ] AH; sampannaṃ JK

68a svara] AJK; mvara H

68b tumburādiṣu] AH; taṃburādiṣu JK

69a cihnavidmati K; cimhnavijñati J; vijñevijñeti A; cihnecihneti H

• saṃśabdair conj.; saṃcchābdaiḥ JK; saṃsthābdair A; saṃsthābdaiḥ H

69d nāditam] JK; nādibhiḥ H; [[tā]]{nā}dibhiḥ A

70a svāṅgottha] em.; svāṅgo[[ccaṃ]]{ttha} A; svāṅgāntha JK; svāḥ śotvā H

• pṛavicārais] AK; pṛavicāres J

70c rūpaṃ tu] HJK; rūpākhyam A

70d bhṛśākhyam te] AJK; bhṛśākhyam teta H

• prakāśitam] AJK; prakāśitām H

71	bhinnāñjananibhākāram antarikṣaṃ prakalpayet śūlāsīmudgaradharaṃ vyālacarmāambarapriyam	Hf249v
72	śaktihasto bhaved agniḥ śukaparyāṅkago 'thavā candragauranibhaḥ pūṣā dhanurbāṇakarārpitaḥ	
73	vivasvān dhūmravarṇābhah kṛtāntasamatejasah pretārūḍhas tathā daṇḍī kāryo digvasanaḥ sadā	Kf231r
74	vikarālam mahākāyam evam eva gṛhakṣatam sahasyaṃ kiṃ tu kartavyaṃ yamaṃ bhinnāñjanaprabham	J1227lower
75	śuklavastraparīdhānaṃ daṇḍapāśakarārpitam vyādhikoṭīsamāyuktaṃ bhīmogranarakāvṛtam	

$\Omega = \text{AHKJ}(\rightarrow\text{D})$, $\alpha = \text{KJ}(\rightarrow\text{D})$, $\beta = \text{AH}$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

71a nibhākāram] AHJ; nibhākār[[ā]]am K

71b antarikṣaṃ] AH; antarikṣa JK

71c dharaṃ] AH; varaṃ JK

71d carmāmbara] em.; carmāmvara A; carmmaṃvara H; carmāvara]JK

72a hasto] AHK; hastā J

72b paryāṅkago] AHK; paryāṅkagā J

72c candra] AH; caṃdraṃ JK

73a vivasvā] AHJ; vivasvāna K • varṇābhah] HJK; varṇarbha A

73b tejasah] em.; Sanderson; tejasā AHJK

73d sadā] AJK; sadāḥ H 74a vikarālam] AJK; vikarāla H

74b evameva] JK; evamevaṃ AH

74c sahasyaṃ] JK; mahāstraṃ A; sahasrā H

• kiṃ tu] AJK; kraṃtu H

75d bhīmogra] AHK; bhīmāgra J

- 76 gandharvaṃ śaṅkhavarṇābhaṃ paṭṭiśāṅkuśasaṃyutam
gandharvakoṭisaṃyukto bhṛṅgaḥ śuklābjasamṇibhaḥ
- 77 ekavakraś caturbāhuḥ śarasūtradhanurdharaḥ
mṛgo dūrvāṅkuraśyāmaś carmāsikarakalpitaḥ
- 78 pitā kṛśataṛaḥ kāryo daṇḍaviṣṭaramaṇḍitaḥ
pitarākhyaiś ca devaiś ca koṭisaṃkhyaiś ca saṃvṛtaḥ
- 79 dauvāriko daṇḍahasto vikaṭaś cipiṭānanaḥ Af264r
pāśadhṛg bisinīpattramudgaśyāmo 'thavā bhavet
- 80 hemābhaś caiva sugrīvaḥ sumūrtiḥ ṭaṅkadaṇḍadhṛk Hf250r
puṣpadantaḥ sutejādhyo bhūṣuṇḍikarasamṇutaḥ

$\Omega = \text{AHKJ}(\rightarrow D)$, $\alpha = \text{KJ}(\rightarrow D)$, $\beta = \text{AH}$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

Before 80b, A inserts 81bd, then marks the portion to be removed.

- 76d bhṛṅgaḥ] em.; bhṛṅga JK; bhṛṅgī AH • śuklābja] JK; śuklābhra AH
77a vaktraś] AHK; vaktra J
77b śara] HJK; [[mantra]]{sara} A
77c mṛgo] AH; mṛga JK
• dūrvāṅkura] AJK; dūrvvāṅku[[sa]]{ra} H
78a kāryo] A; kāryā JK; kāye H
78b daṇḍa] AJK; diṇḍa H • viṣṭara] A; vistara HJK
78c pitarākhyaiś H; pitarā[[ścai]]k{hyai}ś A; pitarākhyaiś] JK
79c dhṛg] em.; dhṛk AJK; dhṛka H • biśinī] AJK; pisinī H
80a sugrīvaḥ] AH; sugrīva JK
80b ṭaṅka] AH; ṭaka JK • daṇḍa] HJK; [[rū]]{daṇḍa} A
80c puṣpadantaḥ] AH; puṣpadaṇḍaḥ JK
80d saṃyutaḥ] K; saṃyuta J; bhūṣitaḥ H; bhūṣitaṃ A

- 81 pracetā māṣavarṇābhaḥ pāśāṅkuśakarārpitaḥ
nāgoparisthitaḥ kāryo nāgakoṭisamāvṛtaḥ
- 82 asuraḥ khaḍgahastaś ca kṛṣṇābhaś carmabhūṣitaḥ
śoṣaḥ kṛśatamaḥ kāryo rājāvartanibhopamaḥ
- 83 ulkāhastas tathā daṇḍī vyādhikoṭisamanvitaḥ
rogo vajramukhaḥ kāryo yaṣṭicchattrakarārpitaḥ
- 84 nānārogasamākīrṇo nānāvyādhisamāvṛtaḥ
vāyuḥ kapotavarnaś ca sapaṭīdhvajamaṇḍitaḥ
- 85 śyenaḥ padmanibhaḥ kāryo nānāpraharaṇānvitaḥ
nāgakoṭisamāyukto mukhyas tuhinasamṇibhaḥ
- 86ab cāpaśūladharaḥ śrīmān tarjanya tarjane rataḥ

Kf231v
J1228upper

$\Omega = \text{AHKJ}(\rightarrow\text{D}), \alpha = \text{KJ}(\rightarrow\text{D}), \beta = \text{AH}$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

81c kāryo] HJK; kāryaḥ A

82a asuraḥ] AHK; [- - -] J 82c śoṣaḥ] AH; šeṣāḥ K; šeṣā J

82d nibhopamaḥ] AH; ni[-]pamaḥ JK

83c vajramukhaḥ] HJK; ba[[hu]]{jra} sukhaḥ A

84c vāyuḥ] AJK; vāyvra H • kapota] AH; kāpāta JK

84d sapaṭī] AH; sapayaṃ K; saparya J

85a śyenaḥ] AJK; śonaḥ H

85d mukhyas] AJK; mukhas H • tuhina] AK; tahina H; tuhana J

• samṇibhaḥ] HJK; sambhavaḥ A

86cd	bhalvāṭo himasaṃkāśaḥ śaktighaṇṭāsamanvitaḥ	Af264v
87	ṣaṇmukho dvādaśabhujō mayūrakṛtavāhanaḥ somo 'mṛtamayo viddhi kalaśāsīsamānviṭaḥ	
88	ṛgyas tu tuhinābhāso daṇḍākṣavalayānviṭaḥ darbhāpicchadharo dhīmān kamaṇḍalukarārpitaḥ	Hf250v
89	lambakūrcō 'ditir viddhi mālāpadmāṅkito jaguḥ ditiś ca raktagaurābhaḥ śaṅkhacakraḍharaḥ sadā	
90	brahmā catuḥpado madhye tasya dhyānaṃ prakāśitam sa marīcir vivasvāṃś ca mitraś ca pṛthivīḍharaḥ	J1228lower Kf232r
91ab	ṣaṭpadās tu samākhyātās teṣāṃ dhyānam uḍīritam	

$\Omega = \text{AHKJ}(\rightarrow\text{D}), \alpha = \text{KJ}(\rightarrow\text{D}), \beta = \text{AH}$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

Before 86b, J and K insert 88a and 88b up to the end of daṇḍākṣa. The insertion is corrected in both manuscripts. The passage is later repeated in its proper position.

- 86d ghaṇṭā] AHK; ghaṇṭhā J
 87a mukho] A; mukha AHK • dvādaśa] AJK; dvādaśa[[dvā]] H
 88a ṛgyas tu tuhinābhāso] A; ṛgikṣṇastittirābhāso K; ṛgikṣṇastittirābhāso J;
 ṛgyajustittirābhāso H
 88b daṇḍākṣa] AJK; daṇḍāṣa H
 88c darbha] AHK; drabha J • dharo] AH; varo JK • dhīmān] AJK; vīmān H
 88d kamaṇḍalu] HJK; kvamaṇḍalu A
 • karārpitaḥ] AHK; karāpitaḥ J 89 kūrco] AH; krūro JK
 • ditir] AH; diti JK • viddhi] AK; viddhir H; vidhi J
 89b mālāpadmāṅkito] AH; mālāpadmāṅkite JK
 • jaguḥ] em. Sanderson; jagah HJK; gajah A
 89c gaurābhaḥ] AHK; gorābhaḥ J
 90c marīcir] em.; marīci A; marīco JK; marīyo H
 90d mitraś ca] A; mitraghnaḥ HJK

- 91cd āpaś caivāpavatsaś ca padikaḥ padikaḥ sthitaḥ
- 92 sāvitriḥ savitā tadvad indra indrajayas tathā
rudro vai rudradāsaś ca padikāḥ parikīrtitāḥ
- 93 aṣṭau koṇagatā devā vijñeyārdhapadasthitāḥ
śeṣās tu padikā jñeyāḥ samkṣepād gr̥havāstutaḥ
- 94 skando 'ryamā jambhakaś ca pilipicchas tu pūrvataḥ
carakī ca vidārī ca pūtanā pāparākṣasī
- 95 īśakoṇāt samārabhya rākṣasyo bāhyataḥ sthitāḥ
sitaraktapītakṛṣṇās ca skandādyā vikṛtānanāḥ

Af265r

$\Omega = \text{AHKJ}(\rightarrow\text{D})$, $\alpha = \text{KJ}(\rightarrow\text{D})$, $\beta = \text{AH}$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

92a sāvitriḥ] A sāvitraḥ HJK

92b indra indra] em.; indrarimdra JK; imdraimdu A; idraridu H

92c rudro] HJK; rorudro K

92d parikīrtitāḥ] AHK; parikīrttitā J

93a aṣṭau] AH; aṣṭa JK

93b vijñeyārdha] A; vijñeyāstu HJK • pada] AJK; pade H

93d samkṣepād] AJK; sam[[jñe]]kṣepād H

94a skando] AH; skanvo JK • 'ryamā] A; [[ma]]ryamā H; yāmā JK

94b pilipicchas tu] K; pilipicchāstu J; pilipimchaśca A; pilipimchastu H

94c carakī] A; ca[[ra]]rakī H; carakrī JK 95b sthitāḥ] HJK; sthitā A

95c kṛṣṇās] AHK; kṛṣṇā J

95d skandādyā] JK; kaṃdādyā H; kāryāvai A

• vikṛtānanāḥ] K; vikṛtānanā AH; kikṛtānanāḥ J

- 96 vajrāsidaṇḍaśūlaṃ ca pāśakādyagadāśiraḥ
skandādyāḥ kathitāḥ samyak carakyādyāḥ śṛṇuṣva ca
- 97 khaḍgakādyāsikṣurikāmuṇḍaghaṇṭāsikartarī
krameṇa saṃyutāḥ kāryā vikṛtās ca kṛśāḥ punaḥ Hf25 1r; J1229upper
- 98 vāstudehe sthitā devāḥ kathitās te mayānagha
vinā dhyānād bhaven mṛtyū rāṣṭrabhaṅgaṃ samādiśet Kf232v
- 99 durbhikṣaṃ balihīne tu homahīne śubhe kṣayaḥ
tasmād yatnāt prakartavyaṃ dhyānadravyakriyānvitam
- 100 iti sarveṣu yāgeṣu vidhānaṃ parikīrtitam

Ω = AHKJ(\rightarrow D), α = KJ(\rightarrow D), β = AH. (D not included in critical apparatus)

- 96a vajrāsi] AJK; viprāsi H • ca] AHJ; tu K 96b kādya] AHK; kādyaṃ J
96c skandādyāḥ] AHK; kadādyāḥ J • kathitāḥ] HJK; kathitā A
96d carakyādyāḥ] A; caraktādyāḥ K; caraktādyā J; rakṣyādyāḥ H
• śṛṇuṣva ca] conj.; śṛṇuṣva JK; śṛṇuṣaṇmukha A; śṛṇu[-]ṇmukha H
97c saṃyutāḥ] AHK; saṃyutā J
97d vikṛtās] AJK; vikṛ[[yā]]ś H • kṛśāḥ] conj.; kṛśāḥ AH; kṛpāḥ JK
98a dehe] AJK; de[[vā]]he H • devāḥ] HJK; devā A
98b mayānagha] AH; mayānaghaḥ JK
98c bhavenmṛtyū] em. Sanderson; bhavenmṛtyu A; bhavetyendram JK;
bhavesyemduṃ H
99a bali] AH; bala JK
99b śubhe kṣayaḥ] JK; subhiṃkṣayaṃ A; śu[-]kṣayem H
100a yāgeṣu] AHK; yogeṣu J

100cd	ekāśītipadaṃ vāstu gr̥hāṇāṃ suprajātmakam	
101	devānāṃ prītidam nāma padāṣṭāṣṭakavartitam nityaṃ śatapadaṃ vidhi susthirākhyam susiddhidam	
102	maṭhadurgapurāṭṭālanagaragrāmakheṭake śayyāsanavimāneṣu tathā baligrheṣv api	
103	siddhisthāne tathā harmye yāgādaḥ parikalpayet vāpīkūpataḍāgādaḥ vaneṣūpavaneṣu ca	Af265v
104	uktānukteṣu sarvatra kuryāt śatapadaṃ suta pañcaviṃśatapadaṃ yac ca vetālākhyam citau matam	
105ab	amarāṇāṃ tu saṃsthāne pañcadhā parikalpayet	J1229lower

$\Omega = \text{AHKJ}(\rightarrow D)$, $\alpha = \text{KJ}(\rightarrow D)$, $\beta = \text{AH}$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

100c-104 is quoted, without attribution, by Trilocana in the Somaśambhupaddhati. See Brunner edition vol. 4, p.47:

devānāṃ prītidam nāma padāṣṭāṣṭavartitam | ekāśītipadaṃ vāstu gr̥hāṇāṃ
suprajātmakam || nityaṃ śatapadaṃ vidhi susthirākhyam susiddhidam | pa
(ttana)dūrgapurāṭṭālanagaragrāmakheṭake || śayyāsanavimāneṣu tathā baligrheṣvapi |
vāpīkūpataḍāgādaḥ vaneṣūpavaneṣu ca || uktānukteṣu sarvatra kāryam śatapadaṃ guha |
pañcaviṃśatapadaṃ yac ca vetālākhyam citau matam ||

100c vāstu] em.; vāstu Trilocana; vāstum AHJK 100d gr̥hāṇāṃ] AHK;
gr̥hīnāṃ J 102a maṭha] JK; [[nava]]{maṭha} A; nava H • purāṭṭāla] HJK;
purā[[tmāna]]{ṭṭāla} A 102b kheṭake] HJK; ceṭake A 102c śayyāsana] AJK;
savyāsana H 102d tathā] HJK; cathā A • bali] em.; bali Trilocana; cala AH; dala JK
103a harmye] A; harme HJK 103b yāgādaḥ] A; yāgādvau K; yāgādvo J; thāgādvau H
104a sarvatra] AJK; sarvva[-] H 104b kuryāt] JK; kāryaḥ A; kārya H
• śatapadaṃ suta] AJK; śaṃtapadaṃsat H 104c yac ca] em.; yacca Trilocana:
yatra AHJK 104d citau] HJK; cito A 105a amarāṇāṃ tu] HJK;
ama{rā}ṇāṃ[[na]]tu[[i]] A

105cd	āvāridarśanaṃ pūjya samapṛṣṭhe tathā punaḥ	
106	tathā brahmaśilāṃ nyāsed vārakasya niveśane sūtrasamsthāpane pūjyaṃ vāstudehaṃ ṣaḍānana	Hf251v
107	pade tu susthiraṃ nāma bhūpṛṣṭhe vāstusaṃjñakam brahmapīṭhād adho vṛddhaṃ sarake vighnamardanam	Kf233r
108	sūtrādho dharmadaṇḍākhyāś cakrapāde ca mandire rajjvaṣṭakaṃ ca sarveṣāṃ vāstūnāṃ samavasthitam	
109	vaṃśadvayaṃ koṇagataṃ durjayaṃ nāma durdharam catuṣṭayaṃ tu rajjūnāṃ ṣaṭpadaṃ dvipadaṃ tathā	
110	vaktragulphaprakoṣṭhābhyāṃ dvipadaṃ syāc catuṣṭayam hṛdi gulphe tathā kukṣau ṣaṭpadaṃ syāc catuṣṭayam	

Ω = AHKJ(\rightarrow D), α = KJ(\rightarrow D), β = AH. (D not included in critical apparatus)

After bhūpṛṣṭhe in 107b, J (and its apograph, D) and K are lacking text until 124d purato nayet. At K, bhūpṛṣṭhe are the last akṣaras on a folio. The situation suggests that J's position in the transmission is that of a descendant of K.

105c āvāri] JK; ācāri AH • darśanaṃ] em. Sanderson; darśane AHJK • pūjya] JK;
pūjyaṃ AH

106a śilāṃ] em.; śilā AHJK

107c brahma] H; brahmā A

108c rajjvaṣṭakaṃ] em.; rājivāṣṭakaṃ A; rajvāmūkaṃ H

109d dvipadaṃ] A; [- - -] H

110a gulpha] A; gu[[gu]]lpha H

110c gulphe] A; guhye H

110d syāc catuṣṭayam] A; [[dyā]]syāātuṣṭayam H

- 111 evaṃ navapade deyaṃ tripadaṃ ṣaṭpadaṃ kramāt
yathā surālaye nyāse mandire tadvad iva hi
- 112 madhye brahmā navapade marīcyādyās tu pūrvavat
āpādyā dvīpadā jñeyā padikā bāhyadevatāḥ
- 113 yathā devālaye nyāsas tathā śatapade hitaḥ
grahāḥ skandādayas tatra vijñeyāś ca catuḥpadāḥ
- 114ab carakyādyā bhūtapadā rajjuvaṃśādī pūrvavat

Af266r

$\Omega = AHKJ(\rightarrow D)$, $\alpha = KJ(\rightarrow D)$, $\beta = AH$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

After bhūprṣṭhe in 107b, J (and its apograph, D) and K are lacking text until 124d purato nayet. At K, bhūprṣṭhe are the last akṣaras on a folio. The situation suggests that J's position in the transmission is that of a descendant of K.

- 111c surālaye] A; sarālaye H
112c āpādyā] em.; apādyā AH
113c skandādayas] A; skaṃdā[-]yas H
113d padāḥ] H; padā A
112a nava] A; nanaca H
112d devatāḥ] H; devatā A
114a carakyādyā] em.; caraādyā A; caraṣṭhādyā H

114cd deśasamsthāpane vāstum catustrimśatsiraṃ bhavet

115 ekāsītīpado brahmā madhyasthāne prakalpayet
sa marīcir vivasvāṃś ca mitraś ca pṛthivīdharah

Hf252r

116 catuḥpañcāśatpadikā āpādy aṣṭau rasāgnibhiḥ
īśānādyā navapadā dvātrimśat parikalpayet

117 vīthikā bhāgamānena rākṣasās tadanantaram
skando 'ryamā jambhakaś ca pilipiccho grahottamaḥ

118 śatikoktās tatthehāpi nyastavyā randhrasamkhyayā
carakyādyās tadvad eva tathā vaṃśadvayaṃ punaḥ

119 rajjvaṣṭakaṃ kramād deyaṃ tathā navapade purā
navabhis tu padai raśmin padam ekaṃ vinirmitam

120ab evaṃ vai deśavāstum tu kathitaṃ te samāsataḥ

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After bhūprṣṭhe in 107b, J (and its apograph, D) and K are lacking text until 124d purato nayet. At K, bhūprṣṭhe are the last akṣaras on a folio. The situation suggests that J's position in the transmission is that of a descendant of K.

114c vāstum] A; vāstumvāstum H

114d catustrimśatsiraṃ] em.; catuḥtrimśacchiraṃ H; catuḥtrimśaśiraṃ A

115c marīcir] em.; mariyo AH • vivasvāṃś ca] A; vivasvā[-] H

116a pañcāśat] H; pañcāśa A

116b āpādy] A; apādy H

116d dvātrimśat] H; trimśatpra A

117c skando] A; skaṃdā H

117d pilipiccho] em.; pilipiccha H; pilipiṃcha A

118a tatthehāpi] A; taṣṭhehāpi H 118c carakyādyās] H; carakapādyās A

119a rajjvaṣṭakaṃ] em.; rajvāṣṭakaṃ H; rakṣāṣṭakaṃ A

• kramād deyaṃ] H; kramādeyaṃ A

120cd	maṇḍalāṅkam evam eva maṇḍale samprakalpayet	
121	kiṃ tu daśasahasrais tu koṣṭhakair vibhajet puram nyāsaṃ navaguṇaṃ tatra kartavyaṃ deśavāstuvat	Af266v
122	athānyaṃ sampravakṣyāmi vāstūnāṃ lakṣaṇaṃ punaḥ ṣaḍāstryaśravṛttābjayonyaṣṭāśrārdhacandravat	
123	tatpadair vāstur vā kāryo rajjuvaṃśavivarjitaḥ madhye tu caturaśraṃ tu sarveṣāṃ vā prakalpayet	
124	rajjuvaṃśasirānyāsaṃ pūrvavat teṣu kalpayet caturaśraṃ tridhā kṛtvā tryaṃśaṃ tu purato nayet	Hf252v
125	lāñchayet tena mānena tad vinā matsakatrāyam tadā śastaṃ trikoṇaṃ tu kṣetramānena jāyate	

$\Omega = \text{AHKJ}(\rightarrow\text{D})$, $\alpha = \text{KJ}(\rightarrow\text{D})$, $\beta = \text{AH}$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

After bhūprṣṭhe in 107b, J (and its apograph, D) and K are lacking text until 124d purato nayet. At K, bhūprṣṭhe are the last akṣaras on a folio. The situation suggests that J's position in the transmission is that of a descendant of K.

120c maṇḍalāṅkam] H; maṇḍalākṣam A

• evam eva] A; eva H

121b puram] H; paraṃ A

121d kartavyaṃ] H; garttavyaṃ A

122d aṣṭāśrārdha] H; aṣṭāārdha A

123a padair] A; pādair H

124a nyāsaṃ] em. Sanderson; nyāsa A; nyāsaḥ H • sirā] em.; sira H; śira A

124c tridhā] em.; tritridhā H; ṛdhā A 124d nayet] AHK; mayet J

125a lāñchayet] AK; lāñcchayet H; nāñtaye J

125c śastaṃ] AH; saptaṃ JK

- 126 gr̥haṃ kuṇḍaṃ maṇḍapaṃ vā kāryam eva surālayam
samatrimekhalopetaṃ kartavyaṃ devatāpadam
- 127 kṣetraṃ ṣaḍbhāgataḥ kṛtvā bhāgārdham purataḥ kṣipet
lāñchayet tena mānena kṣetrārdhān mīnatyurataḥ
- 128 ṣaṣṭūtrapātanāt śastam ṣaṣṭūtram kṣetravad bhavet
ardhāṃśahīnāt pūrvārdhād agnipadojjhitāt
- 129 ardhacandrasamākhyātaṃ prāgardhāt tu paribhramāt
yonis tu pūrvavat kāryā kṣetramānena jāyate

$\Omega = \text{AHKJ}(\rightarrow\text{D})$, $\alpha = \text{KJ}(\rightarrow\text{D})$, $\beta = \text{AH}$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

126a gr̥haṃ AH; gr̥ha JK 126b vā] HJK; ca A • eva] A; etat HJK

126c sama] AH; samaṃ JK

• trimekhalopetaṃ] AH; trimekhalāpetam K; trimeṣalāpetam J

127b purataḥ kṣipet] AJK; punarataḥkṣipeta H

128a śastam] conj. Sanderson; saṣṭam] K; spaṣṭam AH

128c ardhāṃśa] conj.; arkāṃśa AHJK • hīnāt] HJK; hīnā A

• pūrvārdhād] JK; pūrvā[-]d A; pūrvvādapūrvvā H

128d padojjhitān] JK; parojjivān A; parojjitān H

129d prāgardhāt tu] AH; prayārdhāsa JK

- 130 koṇārdhāṣṭāmśatas tyāgāc caturaśraṃ prakalpayet
prākkaṇārdhāmśaṃ cāṣṭāśraṃ dikṣu nyāsāt prajāyate Af267r
- 131 evaṃ vai ṣoḍaśāśraṃ tu dvātriṃśāśrāvadhī kramāt
kalpayet kramaśo vatsa yathā vṛttaṃ prajāyate J1230upper
- 132 caturaśrapramāṇena yathā kṣetraṃ prajāyate
tatheha kalpanīyās tu tryaśrādyā nānyathā hitam
- 133 gṛhe gṛhapramāṇaṃ tu vāstudehaṃ prakalpayet
tataḥ kramapramāṇena vartma devālayeṣv api Kf233v; Hf253r
- 134 garbhād dityantamānaṃ tu kalpyāḥ skandādayas tataḥ
evaṃ vai citivāstu syān maṇḍale 'ṣṭakaraṃ matam
- 135 tathā deśasya saṃsthāne vāpīkūpe catuṣkaram
uktānukteṣu sarvatra pañcahastam prakalpayet

$\Omega = \text{AHKJ}(\rightarrow D)$, $\alpha = \text{KJ}(\rightarrow D)$, $\beta = \text{AH}$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

- 130a koṇārdhāṣṭāmśatas] AK; koṇāddhāṣṭāmśatas J; koṇārdhāmśāmsat H
130c prākkaṇārdhāmśaṃ] em.; prākkaṇārdhāmśa A; prākkaṇārdhāsā H;
prāgkaṇārdhāsā JK • cāṣṭāśraṃ] em.; cāṣṭāśraṃ K; cāṣṭāmśraṃ J; cāṣṭāmśa AH
130d nyāsāt] AJK; nyā[[syā]]sāt H
131b dvāviṃśāśrāvadhī] em. Sanderson; dvātriṃśādvadhī K; dvātriṃśācavadhī
J; dvātriṃśā[-]vadhī A; dvātriṃśāvavimsāvaviṃ H
131c vatsa] JK; vatsam H; vaṃśam A
132b kṣetraṃ] AJ; kṣetra K; kṣetra[[m]] J 133a gṛhe gṛha] JK; gṛhegṛhe AH
133c krama] JK; karma H; krama A 133d vartma] JK; vartya A; varttya H
134a garbhād dity] em.; garbhādnity H; garbhādity A; garbhā[-]ty JK
• anta] AJK; ata H 134b kalpyāḥ] JK; kalpāḥ AH
• skandādayas] AJK; skandādaya H
134c citi] HJK; cita A • vāstu] AJK; vāstuḥ H
134d syān] AH; syāt JK • maṇḍale 'ṣṭa] JK; maṇḍaleṣva AH
135b kūpe] AHK; kūṣe J 135d hastam] AH; hasta JK

- 136 śuddhe śuddhaṃ phalaṃ viddhi miśre miśraphalaṃ bhavet
evaṃ jñātvā prayatnena vāstudehaṃ vivartayet
- 137 pañcaviṃśatpadaṃ yatnāc citivāstum prakalpayet
dikṣitānāṃ prayatnena tathā devālayeṣu ca
- 138 yatnāt pitṛvanākṣipte sthāpaneṣu kṛteṣv api
madhye catuṣpade brahmā dharāsaha niyojayet
- 139 nairṛtyāṃ vāruṇaṃ viṣṇuṃ catuṣpadagataṃ mahat
vāyviśau vāyukoṇe tu agnirudrau tathāgnigau
- 140 īse catuṣpadagatau jñeyau vyomasadāśivau
indro yamo 'tha varuṇaḥ kubero dikṣu koṣthagāḥ

Af267v

J1230lower

$\Omega = \text{AHKJ}(\rightarrow\text{D}), \alpha = \text{KJ}(\rightarrow\text{D}), \beta = \text{AH}$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

With 138c-140d compare SŚ part 3, page 589, verses 12c-15b:

tatra madhye bhuvā sārḍhaṃ brahmāṇaṃ pañcakoṣṭhake
nairṛtyāṃ vāriṇā sārḍhaṃ viṣṇuṃ koṣṭhacatuṣṭaye
agnikoṇe catuṣkoṣṭhe rudraṃ jvalanasamyutaṃ
vāyukoṇe catuṣkoṣṭhe vāyunā samamīśvaram
taccatuṣke tathaiśānyāṃ gaganena sadāśivam
pūrvādidikṣu koṣṭheṣu śakrādīmścaturō 'rcayet

Manuscript A is hard to read in places from verse 137-150. Where I cannot read it, I will leave it out of the apparatus.

- 136b miśre] JK; miśra H; śubhre A 137a viṃśatpadaṃ] A; viṃśatpada H; viśatyamca J
137b yatnāc citi] KJ; yatnāditi A; yatvātnācciti H • vāstum] AH; vāstu J
138a pitṛ] HJK; sitṛ A • vanākṣipte] A; vanākṣipteṣu H; vakūpeṣu J
138c madhye] AJ; madhya H • catuṣ] AJ; catuḥ H
138d dharāsaha] AH; varāsahe J
139a nairṛtyāṃ] em.; nairṛtyāṃ A; nairṛtyā J; nirityāṃ H
139b viṣṇuṃ] HJK; viṣṇu A • catuṣ] em.; catuḥ HJK; caruḥ A • pada] AJK; padaṃ H
139c vāyviśau] AJK; vāthīsau H
139d agnirudrau] JK; agnirudro A; agni[[ho]]rudrau H
140a catuṣ] AJ; catuḥ H • gatau] AJ; śau H
140b vyomasadāśivau] AH; sāṅgamurāśivau J
140c varuṇaḥ] HJK; varuṇo A
140d koṣthagāḥ] em. Sanderson; koṣṭhavā K; ko[-]vā J; cāṣṭadhā A; voṣṭadhā H

- 141 vaṃśaḥ pañcapado jñeyaḥ padikāś ca catuṣpadāḥ
rajjvaṣṭakaṃ samākhyātaṃ vetālāṣṭau ṣaḍānana Hf253v
- 142 vajralāṅgalaśūlādyā maṇibandhādayas tathā
padmasvastikaśuddhākhyāṃ mahāmarmādayas tathā Kf234r
- 143 dvādaśāgryāḥ samākhyātāḥ śatam aṣṭottaraṃ param
tathā sūkṣmaṃ sahasraṃ tu varjanīyaṃ prayatnataḥ
- 144 aṅgulam ardhāṅgulam vā saumyāt sūtraṃ nayet tataḥ
tena sarveṣu marmeṣu dyutir bhavati nānyathā

$\Omega = \text{AHKJ}(\rightarrow\text{D}), \alpha = \text{KJ}(\rightarrow\text{D}), \beta = \text{AH}$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

- 141a vaṃśaḥ] H; vaṃśo A; sarvvaśa JK • pañca] AHK; paca J
• pado] AHK; padau J • jñeyaḥ] H; jñeyo AJK 141b catuṣ] em.; catuḥ AHJK
141c rajjvaṣṭakaṃ] em.; rajvaṣṭakaṃ A; rajvāṣṭakaṃ H; rajvāṣṭaka JK
141d vetālāṣṭau] A; vetālākhye J; vaitālākhye H
142a lāṅgalaśūlādyā] H; lāṃgūlaśūlādyā A;
[-----] J
142b maṇi] AH; maśi J
142c śuddhākhyāṃ] JK; śuddhākhyā AH
142d marmādayas] AJK; mamīdayas H 143a dvādaśāgryāḥ] AH; dvādaśāśrīḥ J
143b param] HJK; padaṃ A 143c sahasraṃ] AH; sahaśra J
143d varjanīyaṃ] AH; varjjanīya J • prayatnataḥ] AH; prayatnata J
144a aṅgulam] AH; [---] J
• ardhāṅgulam vā] AH; [-----] J
144b saumyāt sūtraṃ nayet] em.; saumyāsūtraṃ nayet AH;
[-]myātmaṃvarttayet J

- 145 sampūjya śuklapuṣpais tu sitagandhair vilepanaiḥ
pāyasena tu sarveṣāṃ sakhaṇḍādyena ṣaṇmukha
- 146 naivedyaṃ dāpayed bhaktyā svanāmnā praṇivādinā
namaskārāvasānena sarveṣāṃ jananaṃ hitam
- 147 svāhāntam agnikāryeṣu kalpyāṃśaṃ rākṣaseṣu ca
na māṃsaṃ na surā deyaṃ śāstre 'smin kṛttikāsuta
- 148 mātṛṇāṃ bhairavendrasya sthāpane pūjane tathā
guhyakānāṃ tu daityānāṃ vetālānāṃ tathā punaḥ
- 149 pūjā kāryā prayatnena siddhāntoktena vartmanā
kva madyaṃ kva śive bhaktiḥ kva māṃsaṃ kva bhavārcanam
- 150 madyamāṃsānuraktānāṃ dūre tiṣṭhati śaṅkaraḥ
tasmāt sarvprayatnena śuddhadravyaḥ prapūjayet

Af268r

J1231upper

Hf254r

$\Omega = \text{AHKJ}(\rightarrow\text{D})$, $\alpha = \text{KJ}(\rightarrow\text{D})$, $\beta = \text{AH}$. (D not included in critical apparatus)
J lacks 145ab and 147c, and is hard to read at 148cd-149ab.

with 147c-150 compare the following passages pointed out by Sanderson (email October 2009):

Vāthula quoted in Hṛdayaśiva's Prāyaścittasamuccaya, Cambridge Univ. library, Add. 2833, f.

113v5-114r1: śūdrāṇāṃ dīkṣitānāṃ ca madyapāne kṛte punaḥ | niyamād ayutāc chuddhir aghorāt kṛcchratas
tataḥ | kva madyaṃ kva śive bhaktiḥ kva māṃsaṃ kva bhavārcanam | madyamāṃsapravṛttānāṃ dūre
tiṣṭhati śaṅkaraḥ | "But if an initiated śūdra has drunk intoxicating liquor he can only be purified by ten
thousand Aghora repetitions and a kṛcchra fast. Wine and devotion to Śiva are incompatible and so are
meat and Śiva's worship. Śiva keeps his distance from those that indulge in alcoholic drinks and meat."
The first pāda is quoted by Jayaratha on Tantrāloka 15.560a (vol. 9, p. 272): upadeśāyeti 'kva madyaṃ kva
śive bhaktiḥ' ityādeḥ.

A version of this passage is seen in Śivadharmā 12.9c-10b: kva madyaṃ kva śive bhaktiḥ kva
māṃsaṃ kva śivārcanam || madyamāṃsaprasaktānāṃ dūre tiṣṭhati śaṅkaraḥ. This last is probably the
Bṛhatkālottara's source here.

145a puṣpais tu] HJ; puṣpaiśca A 145b gandhair vilepanaiḥ] AH; gaṃdhānulepanai J 145d
ṣaṇmukha] A; tuṣaṇmukha H
146a naivedyaṃ] H; naivaidyaṃ A 146b sva] AH; stu J • nāmnā] em.; nāma AHJ
146c kārāvasānena HJ; kārāvasānetu A 146d hitam] AH; hitaṃhitam J
147b kalpyāṃśaṃ] em. Sanderson; kalpāṃśaṃ AH; kalpāsaṃ J• rākṣaseṣu] AH; vaṅgameṣu J
147c māṃsaṃ] AJ; māsaṃ H• deyaṃ] H; deyā A 147d śāstre 'smin] AH; [-] stresmin J
148b sthāpane] AJ; sthāne H 149b vartmanā] A; vatmānā H
149c bhaktiḥ] HJ; bhakti A 150a madyamāṃsānuraktānāṃ A; madyamāṃsaturaktānāṃ H;
madrāmāṃsaraktānāṃ K; madirāmāṃsaraktānāṃ J 150d śuddha] AJK; tuddha H

- 151 dadhikṣīrodakaṃ teṣāṃ pānam uktaṃ śivena tu
siddhāntoktena vidhinā pūjyaṃ siddhāntakovidaiḥ
- 152 vāmācāraiḥ svakair dravyaiḥ pūjā kāryā krameṇa tu
siddhāntoktaṃ na vāme tu vāmācāraṃ na dakṣiṇe
- 153 yo yatraiva vidhiḥ proktaḥ sa tatraiva phalapradaḥ
kravyādatvaṃ tu sa balāt siddho 'pi narakaṃ vrajet
- 154 tasmāt sarvaprayatnena svanayoktena saṃcaret

Kf234v

iti kālottare mahātantre vāstuyāgapaṭalam

$\Omega = \text{AHKJ}(\rightarrow\text{D}), \alpha = \text{KJ}(\rightarrow\text{D}), \beta = \text{AH}$. (D not included in critical apparatus)

152a vāmācāraiḥ] AJK; vāmācāraiḥ H • svakair dravyaiḥ] AJK; sva[-]dravyaiḥ H

152cd na vāme tu vāmācāraṃ na] AJK; navāmācāraṃna H

153c balāt] AJK; balā H

154b saṃcaret] JK; saṃbhavet AH